

An Overview of Phonological Processes and Theories in English

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Abstract

This study is an overview of phonological processes and theories in English; it brings the features and principles of phonological processes and theories to the fore, and establishes the systematic nature of speech production by the human organs of speech. Essentially therefore, the study is immersed in phonetics and phonology. While phonetics is the study of the acoustic properties of discrete sounds (consonants and vowels), phonology is the study of the underlying rules and principles that govern the combination of sounds. Without sounds, words cannot exist, and linguistic stretches cannot be constructed. Thus, sounds are the basis for the study of any language. This study concludes that phonological processes (e.g. assimilation, co-articulation, elision, deletion, etc.) and theories (e.g. Metrical Phonology Theory, under specification Theory, Isochrony Theory, Morpho-phonemics Theory, etc.) in English reveal that at the levels of words and linguistic stretches, natural speech production in humans is procedural towards effective articulation of segments.

Keywords: *phonetics, phonology, phonological processes, phonological theories, vowels, consonants.*

1. Introduction

Phonological theories have an age-long tradition of explaining the internal structure of human languages. According to Richard Wiese (2006, p. 562) “while the groundwork for phonology was laid in the analysis of many ancient and modern languages, around the beginning of the 20th century the work by Ferdinand de Saussure (Saussure, 1916), Jan Baudouin de Courtenay (Baudouin de Courtenay, 1972), and Franz Boas (Boas, 1889) was crucial for the formulation of the phonemic analysis in a stricter sense. This was followed in the first half of the 20th century by several important formulations of phonological theory, notably by Edward Sapir (Sapir, 1921), Leonard Bloomfield (Bloomfield 1933), Roman Jakobson (Jakobson 1939) and Nikolay Trubetzkay (Trubetzkoy, 1967) ...” A study of phonological processes and theories in any language attempts the elucidation of speech sounds and their patterning from different perspectives. Ramelan (1994) submits that “the study of speech sounds may be carried out from different viewpoints. When we study speech sounds as sounds, without regard to their function as signaling units of language, the science is called ‘phonetics’ ...” This study is poised to show that phonological processes and theories in English explain the structure of the language beyond the level of the phoneme, by capturing cognition level which concerns the internal and systematic rules that generate intelligibility via the morpho-phonemic rules of the language, as evident in the sound-driven interaction between words and linguistic stretches.

2. Phonetics and Phonology

Phonetics examines discrete sounds (phonemes) of a language. Such sounds (vowels and consonants) are described in terms of what is referred to as their “phonetic properties”. To combine sounds meaningfully (significantly) in a language, certain systematic rules, processes and principles are involved. Phonology is the study of the rules, processes and principles that govern the combination or patterning of sounds in a given language. Phonology is divided into: segmental phonology and suprasegmental phonology. While segmental phonology studies the individual phonemes in a language, suprasegmental phonology examines prosodic features of speech production: stress, intonation, pitch and rhythm) in words and linguistic stretches. For comprehensive insights on segmental and suprasegmental features of vowel and consonant sounds, see Adekunbi (1999) and Roach (2000).

3. Phonological Processes and Theories in English

This section of the paper examines phonological processes and theories in English.

3.1 Phonological Processes in English

Five phonological processes in English are briefly examined as follows:

3.1.1 Assimilation

Assimilation is the combination of morphemes to change one phoneme into another. It is a morpho-phonemic change. Based on the particular sound that influences an assimilated sound, two types of assimilation are known in the literature: progressive assimilation (an influence based on preceding sound) and regressive assimilation (an influence based on a following sound). Changes in the assimilated sounds can be construed in terms of place of articulation, manner of articulation and voicing (cf. Ramelan 1994, p. 173). Assimilation can be complete or partial based on whether the assimilated sound is completely changed into the same sound as the sound that affects the change or not. Examples of regressive assimilation are as follows:

- a.) “partial” /pa:ʃl/; “impartial” /ɪmpa:ʃl/
- b.) “possible” /pɔ:səbl/; “impossible” /ɪmˈpɔ:səbl/
- c.) “proper” /ˈprɒpə/; “improper” /ɪmˈprɒpə/
- d.) “direct” /daɪˈrekt/; “indirect” /ɪndaɪˈrekt/
- e.) “correct” /kəˈrekt/; “incorrect” /ɪnkəˈrekt/;
- f.) “visible” /ˈvɪsəbl/; “invisible” /ɪnˈvɪsəbl/;

An example of progressive assimilation is the linguistic stretch below:

“It’s there now.” /ɪt ɪz ðeə nau/

The change from /s/ to /z/ is the influence of a preceding voiced sound. The reverse is the case when the preceding sound is not voiced. Assimilation captures the influence of one phoneme on another as a result of their close phonetic environment. For instance, a vowel is nasalized before a vowel sound as the velum is lowered in advance to realize nasal sound as in “can’t” /kænt/. This is an example of regressive assimilation in which the nasalization is backwards to capture a preceding phoneme. “Voicing”, “devoicing” and “flapping” are types of assimilation. Assimilation can also be categorized from the viewpoints of place of articulation. Voicing takes place when voiceless liquids and glides occur after voiceless stops as in “please” /pli:z/ and “pride” /praɪd/; the sounds are devoiced in such phonetic environments. Based on phonetic-environment-driven influence of one sound on the another, the following are also examples of assimilation:

- a.) permeable/impermeable;
- b.) tolerable/intolerable;
- c.) tangible/intangible;
- d.) possible/impossible;

In flapping, a dental or alveolar stop changes to a flap /ɾ/ as in the realization of /t/ and /d/ between vowels. In such a situation, stress is on the first segment. Examples of flapping are in the articulation of the words “spinster”, “matter”, “winter” and “writer”.

3.1.2 Dissimilation

Dissimilation results in two phonemes becoming less similar as in the articulation of words ending with three consecutive fricatives. In the production of the word “faiths”, /ˈfeɪθs/ is realized with the removal of the voiceless dental fricative /θ/. Similarly, when the word “myths” is pronounced, /mɪθs/ is realized instead of /mɪθs/.

3.1.3 Deletion

Connected speech is typical of deleting certain phonemes as a characteristic of proficient speech production. This process is referred to as deletion; the deletion of /ə/ before a following stressed vowel is an example of such a phonological process as in the following transcribed words:

‘marriage’ /^lmærIdz/; /^lmrIdz/

‘carriage’ /^lKærIdz/; /^lkrIdz/

3.1.4 Coarticulation

The pronunciation of words with one or more syllables is made effective through the process of coarticulation, which has to do with combining contiguous sounds. The process is enabled by the organs of speech. Proficient speaking is hindered when sound segments are not coarticulated in connected speech (rapid speech). Michael Dobrovolsky’s (2004) submits that “due to the rapidity of speech (we can produce many segments in a second) and the design of the vocal tract, if our goal is to produce a [pl] sequence, we cannot make the [p] and then make the [l]. Indeed, early speech synthesizers that produce speech this way were practically unintelligible. Rather as the sequence [pl] is produced, the tongue tip will start to move toward the alveolar ridge before the lips separate. The term coarticulation is used for situations such as this in which more than one articulator (here the lips and the tongue tip) is active ...¹”

3.1.5 Elision

Elision is a morph-phonemic process of dropping sounds when morphemes are close to each other and because of their occurrences in unstressed syllables or in rapid speech. In rapid speech, sound segments are naturally omitted in certain phonetic contexts. A common phonological process in English, elision can be contextual. Taiwo Soneye (2018) notes that “contextual elision deals with a sound that exists in a word said in isolation but it is dropped when preceding another word. It is, according to Li-hua (2013: 728), formed in continuous spoken chains according to adjacent phonemes as well as speed time and volume of the speech.” Roach (1983, p. 108) posits that sounds can either disappear in certain phonological circumstances or have zero realization as in:

- a) “Next door” /nekst dɔ:/ pronounced as “nes door” /nesdɔ:/ with the dropping of /k/ and /t/ in “next”; and
- b) “Must go” /mæstgəu/ pronounced as “mus go” /mæsgəu/ with the dropping of /t/ in “must”.
- c) “Last month” /la:stm[^]nθ/ is pronounced as “las month” /la:sm[^]nθ/ with the dropping of /t/ in “last”.

The following features or principles of elision should be noted:

- a.) /t/ is zero-realization before /d, g, m, n/;
- b.) The phonetic properties of /t/ and /d/ are same except for voice;
- c.) /t/ is dropped before voiced alveolar sound;
- d.) /t/ is dropped before voiced velar stop (plosive);
- e.) /t/ is dropped before voiced bilabial nasal sound;
- f.) /t/ is dropped before voiced alveolar nasal; and
- g.) /t/ is dropped before voiced consonants.

3.2 Phonological Theories in English

The literature of phonology is replete with phonological theories. This section of the paper examines them briefly:

3.2.1 Metrical Phonology (MP)

Through the use of tree-diagram representations, Metrical Phonology Theory explains rhythmic patterns of words and linguistic stretches. The theory uses letters (S for strong; and W for weak) to signify the strong and weak nodes in syllables, in relation to root (R). Roach (1992) submits that the rhythmic nature of speech and the structure of the foot are crucial components of Metrical Phonology. In this regard, the theory elucidates context-sensitive word stress shifting. In Metrical Phonology Theory, the degree of prominence of syllables as informed by stress, are grouped. Thus, segments are organized into syllables, syllables into metrical feet, feet into phonological words and words into larger units as represented in metrical trees and grids. According to Kager (1995: 367) stress is considered:

Cumulative in MP (content words contain at least one stressed syllable); hierarchical; delimitative in some languages where stressed and unstressed syllables alternate and where clashes (adjacent clashes) are avoided; enhanced segmentally through vowel lengthening or by germination².

3.2.2 Isochrony Theory

The Isochrony Theory is concerned with rhythm-driven durational length of speech production. Rhythm is simply the organization and production of speech within perceivable time or duration. According to Osisanwo (1986), speech rhythm is “a regular succession of one type of sound feature or the other used in achieving melody and sometimes, meaning in a human language.” Rhythm is achieved via stress (primary and secondary stress) placement on syllables. The concept of rhythm is crucial in the Isochrony Theory. Pike (1945) asserts that “the rhythm of a language is determined by how chest-pulses and stress-pulses recur and their mode of succession and coordination.” The two types of rhythm are established: stress-timed rhythm and syllable-timed rhythm (cf. Pike *ibid.*). While syllable-timed rhythm is that in which “the periodic recurrence of movement is supplied by the syllable producing the chest-pulses, stress-timed rhythm concerns the periodic recurrence of movement is supplied by the stress-producing process – isochronous stress pulse and stress syllables. Bouzon and Hirst (2004) evolve “strict isochrony” and “weak isochrony”. While the former posits that the different elements would be exactly equal in duration, the latter explains that equal duration is likely among different elements.

3.2.3 Morphophonemic Theory (Morphophonemics)

In English as in other languages, words accommodate sounds. Morphological constraints determine the phonetic properties of discrete sounds. This situation is the thrust of the Morpho-phonemic Theory. William O’ Grady and Videa de Guzman (2004) assert that “... an /æ/ that occurs in front of a nasal consonant will be nasalized (e.g., [kænt] ‘can’t’ vs. [kæt] ‘cat’), an /æ/ that occurs before a voiceless consonant (e.g., [hæ:d] ‘had’ vs. ‘hat’), and so on. Pronunciation can also be sensitive to morphological factors including words’ internal structure. The study of this phenomenon is known as morphophonemics ... Morphophonemic phenomena are extremely common in language. A famous example from English involves the way that we pronounce the plural suffix -s ...”

3.2.4 Interference and Intraference

The internal system of languages differs in sounds and grammar. Thus, mother tongue (MT) linguistic forms (grammar) interfere with those of a foreign language (FL), resulting in the transfer of the linguistic features of MT into FL. It is a common phenomenon in English as Second Language (ESL) situations. Interference is an inter-language phenomenon while intraference is an intra-language phenomenon. Ekundayo Omowumi Bode (2018) comments on both interference and intraference:

Interference is associated with the concepts of Contrastive Analysis and Language Transfer which are based on the assumptions that second language learners have the tendency of transferring the features of their native and/or first language to their second language utterances (James, 1980, p. 14). Another term for interference is negative transfer, which manifests at all the levels of linguistic organization. The most common in ESL are the phonological types in which the normative speakers impose the fossilized phonological system of their native languages on their second language, at the segmental and suprasegmental levels, which make non-native Nigerian English accent sounds different from native English accents, such as the Received Pronunciation (RP) and General American English (GAmE) ...

The application of the word intraference may be traced several independent outstanding works separated by time and long distances ... Croft (2000) says that “different elements of the same language can interfere with each other if they share enough linguistic substance”, and the intraference occurs when language items are affected by different dialects, sociolinguistic variants or other structures of the same language (pp. 111-165). According to Ekundayo (2000), intraference is “the habit of transferring the rules and dynamics of a language from a section where they have been established and where they acceptably operate to another section within the language where they hitherto used not to operate. Since such a transfer is within the language, it is better tagged intraference, which is the reverse of interference” ... the interplay of cognitive sociolinguistic and linguistic dynamics makes a language user produce intraference features. When a new idea or experience confronts language users, they fall back on the dynamics, loopholes and rules of the language (re)deploy them to convey the new experience or idea. This effort may generate a new linguistic structure, or an existing term may be expanded to accommodate an additional meaning for the new experience (pp. 16-20). Intraference features emanate from the reassignment and redeployment of the items of a language that normative speakers/writers have in their competences to hitherto new areas and contexts. The linguistic factor generates the five major types of intraference: phonological, morpho-syntactic and lexico-semantic with many subdivisions ...

3.2.5 Phonological Sensitivity Skills

As part of linguistic competence, speakers can explore individualistic awareness and mastery of the morphophonemics of sounds and transfer such mastery or knowledge to practical situations of language use (spoken communication). Sounds are not arbitrarily constituents of words; the combination of the former and the latter is essentially part of the internal system of any language. Consciousness of the constituent structures of words in terms of phonetic properties is instrumental in individualistic demonstration of phonological sensitivity skills. Taiwo Soneye (1992) reports Stanovich (1986, p. 362) who defines phonological sensitivity skills as “conscious access to the phonemic level of the speech

stream and the ability to cognitively manipulate representations of this level.” Phonemic awareness/sensitivity according to Ball and Blachman (1991) is the ability to recognize that a spoken word consists of a sequence of individual sounds. Within the phonological sensitivity skills theorizing, the notion “awareness” captures gradable competence on phonological “structure” rather than “sense”.

3.2.6 Phonotactic Theory (Phonotactics)

Phonotactics explains the specifications of a well-formed word in a given language; it analyzes the phonological combinations (constituents) of words. For example, while “drag” is a possible word in English, “rdag” is not. John A. Goldsmith (1995) lists the possibilities that have been considered:

- a) A well-formed word is one that is produced by taking an input string created by the morphological component, and applying the phonological rules of the language in the appropriate order.
- b) A well-formed word is one that consists of a sequence of well-formed syllables.
- c) A well-formed word is one in which all features (or autosegments) are associated to an appropriate skeletal position; all skeletal positions are associated with a syllable; and all syllables are associated with a foot.
- d) A well-formed word is one that simultaneously satisfies all the well-formedness conditions of the language (including those given in (c)).

3.2.7 Underspecification Theory

Underspecification Theory has to do with the placement (and the degree of such placement) of feature distinctions in phonological representations. John A. Goldsmith (ibid.) cites Donca Steriade who posits that within the framework of underspecification, the appearance of feature distinctions in a phonological representation is “not is not as a choice between +F and – F, but rather as a choice between + F and no marking at all”. Types of underspecification identified include trivial (or inherent, or permanent) and nontrivial underspecification (if a feature is allowed to take on only a value). There are contentious positions in the literature concerning the Underspecification Theory; John A. Goldsmith (ibid.) reports:

There are questions that lie behind this disagreement that go even beyond the character of underspecification theory. Kiparsky’s investigation of featural underspecification brings one to a conclusion that we might summarize in the following way: What we have traditionally referred to as ‘lexical diffusion’ is nothing more nor less than the grammar of the language attempting to balance off the relative complexity of rule statements and of lexical entries, the two major components of the grammar. Kiparsky proposes, first of all, and in line with widely understood principles of lexical phonology, that in any particular phonological context, there will be, for any given feature F, an expected, or unmarked, value; this will either be + F or – F. Whether the unmarked value is + F or – F depends very much on the phonological context C, and if the unmarked value of F in context C is + F, then the marked value will be – F ... The second way ... is to look at the relative complexity of the information packed into the rule component and the lexical component of the grammar. Let us recall that from the traditional generative point of view, a phonological grammar is divided into two major components: a set of rules, broadly construed, and a lexicon. The lexicon contains (among other things) the underlying phonological representation of all of the words of the language. The traditional generative concern has been to select the least complex grammar consistent with the data of the language.

Scholars hold the view that feature distinctions will not suffice in explaining the nature of the established contrasts (binary contrasts) in the literature of phonology. It is believed that the notion of specification has to be explained with a more systematic, sophisticated and scientific framework³.

3.2.8 Generative Phonology Theory

The Generative Phonology Theory is based on the assignment of accurate phonetic representations to utterances as a reflection of native speakers’ internalized grammar. The founders of the theory are Noam Chomsky and Morris Halle – in the late 1950s. The thrust of the theory is that native speakers exhibit linguistic competence by producing infinite phonological structures via the syntactic component of grammar, and such a process can be scientifically (systematically) explained. Within the framework of the Generative Phonology Theory, phonological rule or process is usually context-driven; it can apply in discrete points of the same phonological process.

4. Conclusion

Phonological processes and theories are crucial aspects of the study of phonetics (phonemes in a language) and phonology (the linguistic constraints, rules or principles that govern the combination of phonemes). In the explanation of phonological processes and theories in English, this study provides insights on the consonant and vowel sounds of the language. Some of the processes (e.g. elision, deletion, coarticulation) and theories (e.g. the Morpho-phonemic Theory, the Phonotactic Theory, the Metrical Phonology Theory) are about the internal system of language. Others capture interlanguage phenomena (e.g. interference). Given the global status and roles of the English language, a study of its internal system – mechanism for the formation of its sounds as evident in the phonological processes and theories in the

literature – is worthy of scholarly attention. Indeed by extension, this study is a springboard for the elucidation of phonological processes and theories in other natural (human) languages. In human languages – as in the English language – the production of sounds is not an arbitrary process. It is a complex, but systematic mechanism; the phonological processes and theories examined in this study accentuate this claim.

Notes

¹ Although there are different phonological processes in English, the concept “processes” is also used in the literature to refer to “efficient speech production via the combination, dropping or modification of segments in speech production”. For example, Michael Dobroolsky (ibid.) notes that “... when speakers pronounce [k] as more palatal in a word such as key they are speaking more efficiently from the point of view of articulation since they are making a less drastic adjustment in moving from articulation of a more palatal [k] to that of high front vowel than they would make in moving from a velar [k] to a high front vowel ...”

² Stress and intonation are crucial components of the Metrical Phonology Theory since they capture pitches and rhythm. Stress is about loudness of a syllable. Jones (1972) posits that stress is “the degree of force with which a speaker pronounces a word or a syllable.” In English RP (Received Pronunciation, stress types include: primary stress, secondary stress and weak stress.

Intonation is defined by Binkert (1999, p. 188) as “a pitch or change in pitch in a syllable of a word that is associated with a difference in meaning.”

³ For insights on feature distinctions, see Adekunbi Ofuya (1999).

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